

Comparative Evaluation of Solar Tent Drying Efficiency and Product Quality for Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) and Hake (*Merluccius spp.*)

Adeoye Ibukun OYEBANJI ^{1*}, Samuel Emeka CHUKWU ¹, Iyanuoluwa Blessing ADEDIRAN ²
Abdulqadir Tosho OPOBIYI ³, David Ahmed ADAMU ⁴, Owolabi Aminat USMAN ⁵
Bashirat Kikelomo ABDULKAREEM ⁶

¹ Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute, Postharvest Engineering Research Department, Ilorin, Nigeria

² Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute, Perishable Crops Research Department, Ilorin, Nigeria

³ Kwara State University, Department of Food and Agricultural Engineering, Ilorin, Nigeria

⁴ Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute, Research Outreach Department, Ilorin, Nigeria

⁵ Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute, Research Outreach Department, Ilorin, Nigeria

⁶ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Department of Agricultural Engineering Services, Ilorin, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: obanjiometer87@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study investigates the drying efficiency and product quality of two economically significant non-fatty fish species, Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) and Hake (*Merluccius spp.*), using a solar tent dryer. The objective was to optimize dryer configurations, focusing on vent number and polyethylene covering materials to balance drying performance with product quality. The dryer, comprising a metal frame covered with either low-density polyethylene (LDPE, 50 µm) or medium-density polyethylene (MDPE, 250 µm), was tested under three ventilation regimes (2, 4, and 6 vents). A Face-Centered Central Composite Design (FCCCD) within Response Surface Methodology (RSM) assessed the effects of these variables on internal drying conditions. Across 30 experimental trials, temperature and relative humidity were monitored, and data were analysed using ANOVA and Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT) at a 5% significance level. The result shows that covering material and its interaction with fish species significantly affected internal temperature, with LDPE and MDPE achieving thermal retention up to 42 °C. Increased venting reduced temperature but raised humidity, indicating a trade-off between ventilation and thermal efficiency. A consistent U-shaped diurnal humidity profile was observed. Species-specific drying responses emerged: Hake dried faster and reached lower final moisture content, while Blue Whiting retained superior sensory properties, particularly colour and texture. Microbial analysis demonstrated significant reductions in viable bacterial counts post-drying. The findings highlight the critical influence of dryer design on solar drying efficiency, product safety, and sensory quality, offering practical insights for improving fish drying processes in resource-limited settings. It is strongly suggested that similar research should be replicated in other states or regions for effective and conclusive submission vis-à-vis establishing one in optimal conditions for the sampled fish storage and processing.

Keywords: Solar tent dryer, fish drying efficiency, ventilation configuration, species-specific drying

1. Introduction

Fish is a critical component of global food security, particularly in regions where it provides essential animal protein and livelihoods (FAO, 2022). Among the numerous species available, Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) and Hake (*Merluccius spp.*) stand out for their economic value, lean meat, and high-quality protein content (Heffernan et al., 2022). However, their high moisture content makes them highly perishable, necessitating efficient postharvest preservation techniques (Clucas and Ward, 1996). Drying is one of the oldest and most effective methods for extending fish shelf life, improving product stability, and reducing both transportation and storage costs while maintaining most of the nutritional content (Speranza et al., 2021). However, traditional open sun drying methods, commonly used in many parts of Africa and Asia, expose fish to environmental contaminants such as dust, insects, and microbial agents, often compromising hygiene and inconsistent product quality (Bala, 2017). To address these limitations, improved technologies such as solar tent dryers have been developed to enhance drying efficiency and product safety by providing controlled temperature and humidity environments. Solar tent dryer, which was originally developed in Bangladesh, uses a transparent polythene sheet supported by a wooden frame to trap solar heat, creating a greenhouse effect (Doe and Ahmed, 1977). This design raises internal temperatures while allowing the regulated flow of air, facilitating moisture removal more efficiently than open drying (Bala and Mondol, 2020; Fudholi et al., 2010). Solar tent dryers not only enhance drying efficiency but also significantly reduce contamination, offering a sustainable, low-cost option suitable for smallholder fish processors. Despite advances in solar drying technology, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding how different fish species respond to varying dryer configurations. Most existing studies focus on optimizing dryer design or comparing traditional and improved methods, with limited attention given to species-specific drying

behavior under controlled experimental conditions (Mehta et al., 2018). Anatomical and biochemical differences between fish species, such as fat content, muscle structure, and moisture distribution, can significantly influence drying kinetics and final product quality (Erkan and Özden, 2008). This study addresses this gap by systematically comparing Blue Whiting and Hake, two commercially significant, non-fatty fish species-under different solar tent dryer configurations. The novelty of this work lies in its integrated approach: evaluating how both the number of vents (2, 4, or 6) and covering material (low-density vs. medium-density polyethylene) affect drying efficiency and product quality for each species. This research provides new insights into the interplay between dryer parameters and species-specific drying responses by employing a rigorous experimental design and statistical analysis. The findings aim to inform best practices for small-scale fish processors and guide the development of tailored drying technologies that minimize postharvest losses and improve food quality in fish-dependent communities.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental equipment and materials

The experiment was conducted using a solar tent dryer provided by the Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute (NSPRI), Ilorin, Nigeria. The dryer featured a metallic frame and was covered with two types of polyethylene sheets: low-density polyethylene (LDPE) of 50 μm thickness and medium-density polyethylene (MDPE) of 250 μm thickness. The structural dimensions of the dryer were as follows: 170 cm in height, 184 cm in top length, and 250 cm in width (Figure 1). Two commercially available fish species, Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutassou*) and Hake (*Merluccius spp.*), were selected for the study due to their economic and nutritional importance. The fish samples were procured fresh, then subjected to standard preparation procedures including washing, degutting, filleting, and weighing to ensure uniformity across trials.

Equipment used in the study included a digital weighing scale (Model: SF-400), a thermo-hygrometer (Model: HTC-1), an

anemometer (Model: GM816), and stainless-steel knives for sample preparation.

Figure 1. Isometric view of the Tent

2.2 Description and working principle of the solar tent dryer

The solar tent dryer operates on the greenhouse and convective drying principles. The transparent polyethylene material allows solar radiation to penetrate the drying chamber, causing a rise in internal temperature. Cool

ambient air enters the dryer through side vents, absorbs heat, and evaporates moisture from the fish. The warm, moisture-laden air then exits through the top vents, maintaining a continuous drying cycle (Figure 2). This system ensures gradual dehydration, preserves nutritional quality, and improves the shelf life of the dried fish.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the dryer with arranged fishes on the racks

2.3 Experimental design

The drying trials were carried out following a Face-Centered Central Composite Design (FCCCD) under the framework of Response Surface Methodology (RSM) using Design Expert 9.0 software. Two independent variables were investigated: number of vents

(2, 4, and 6) and covering material (LDPE and MDPE), as shown in Table 1. A total of 30 experimental runs were performed, each repeated three times for accuracy. Each run involved arranging approximately 360 g of filleted fish (Blue Whiting or Hake) in the dryer and monitoring drying progress.

Table 1. Factors and Levels Used in FCCCD Experimental Design

Factor	Symbol	Level -1	Level 0	Level +1
Number of Vents	A	2	4	6
Covering Material	B	LDPE	-	MDPE

2.4. Statistics analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 16.0. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significance of the main effects and interactions at a 5% significance level ($P < 0.05$). Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT) was used for mean separation. Environmental parameters such as ambient and internal temperatures and relative humidity were recorded every 8 hours using the thermo-hygrometer. A control experiment using open-sun drying was also performed for comparative analysis.

2.5. Drying process and sample evaluation

The drying experiment was conducted during November and December 2023 at NSPRI. A total of 15 kg of fish (approximately 7.5 kg per species) were used. Post-filleting, the fish were evenly distributed within the solar tent dryer. Each fish type was subjected to varying combinations of vent numbers and covering materials. Upon completion of drying, the samples were placed in a desiccator to prevent moisture reabsorption. Subsequent proximate analysis (moisture, protein, lipid, ash content) was conducted using standard AOAC methods. Sensory evaluation and microbial load assessments were also performed to determine product quality.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Air temperature dynamics during drying

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results shown in Table 2 indicates that air temperature during the drying process was significantly affected by the type of covering material (Factor D), the quadratic effect of drying time (B^2), and the interaction between fish type and covering material (AD). Conversely, the number of vents (A) and the linear effect of drying time (B) did not exhibit statistically significant effects on the drying performance. The observed variations in air temperature within the solar tent dryer across different drying times, covering materials, and vent configurations align with findings reported in contemporary solar drying research. The significant effect of covering material (Factor D) on internal temperature, particularly with polyethylene sheets (LDPE and MDPE), corroborates the work of Jain et al., (2023), who demonstrated that plastic films with low thermal conductivity significantly enhance thermal gain and retention in passive solar dryers. Similarly, Sagar and Kumar (2010) highlighted that the use of polyethylene in solar dryers can increase internal air temperature by 15–25% compared to mesh coverings, thereby improving drying efficiency.

Table 2. Analysis of variance of the studied variables

Source	SS	Df	MS	F Value	Prob > F	Sig
Model	487.7	5	93	32.86	< 0.0001*	Significant
A-No of vent	11.88	1	11.88	4.17	0.0522	ns
B- DryingTime (h)	0.38	1	0.38	0.13	0.7174	ns
C-Type of fish	0.82	1	0.82	0.32	0.5792	
D-Type of covering material	27.01	1	27.01	9.49	< 0.0051*	
AD	63.12	1	63.12	22.17	0.0001*	
B^2	271.16	1	271.16	95.25	0.0001*	
Residual	48.93	19	2.58			
Lack of Fit	68.93	22	3.10	40.35	0.0245	significant
Pure Error	0.15	2	0.077			
Cor Total	536.02	29				

The rise in temperature from under 20 °C to over 35 °C as drying progressed, followed by a decline after 20 hours as illustrated in Figure 3, reflects the typical diurnal thermal cycle observed in tropical environments. This trend is consistent with Fudholi et al. (2010), noted that peak internal dryer temperatures are generally attained between midday and early afternoon, followed by gradual cooling as solar radiation diminishes. The significant quadratic effect of drying time (B^2) observed in this study further supports the nonlinear thermal dynamics influenced by solar intensity and ambient climatic fluctuations, as previously reported by Mehta et al. (2018). Figure 3, 4 and 5 illustrated the implications of the sampled parameters; the thrust of this; shows a progressive increase in air temperature; from approximately 27 °C to 38 °C—as drying time extended from 8 to 24 hours across different covering materials. This rise is primarily attributed to the superior thermal retention properties of materials such as polyethylene. The significant influence of covering material (Factor D), as confirmed by ANOVA,

underscores its critical role in improving drying efficiency through effective heat retention and reduced heat loss. In addition, Figure 5 highlights the interactive effect of vent number and covering material on internal temperature demonstrates the delicate balance between thermal insulation and convective cooling. The reduction in temperature with increasing vent numbers mirrors findings by Dissa et al. (2009), observes that additional vents enhance airflow but can also increase heat dissipation, particularly in low-mass dryers. The results showed a temperature drop from 40 °C to 35 °C as vents increased from 2 to 6, affirming that excessive ventilation may compromise heat retention if not counterbalanced with proper covering material. In contrast, transitioning from net to LDPE or MDPE significantly boosted internal temperature due to reduced convective losses, an effect also highlighted by Banout et al. (2011), who emphasized the importance of enclosure design in maximizing solar energy utilisation.

Figure 3. Effect of Time of Drying on the Air Temperature

Figure 4. Effect of Type of Covering Material (D) on the Air Temperature

Figure 5. Effect of Type of Covering material (D) and Number of

3.2. Role of ventilation and covering material interactions

3.3.1. Humidity regulation within the drying chamber

The ANOVA results (Table 3) reveal that internal humidity levels within the solar tent dryer were statistically significantly and influenced by covering material ($p = 0.0051$), the interaction between vent number and covering material (AD, $p < 0.0001$), and the quadratic effect of drying time (B^2 , $p <$

0.0001). However, the main effects of fish type, linear drying time, and linear vent number were not statistically significant. Nevertheless, interaction effects provided valuable insights into system behavior. On the other hand, humidity trends observed in this study followed a U-shaped pattern over time (Figure 6), decreasing initially and then rising after 16–20 hours. This is in agreement with Behera et al. (2022), who reported that relative humidity inside solar dryers is lowest during peak sun hours and tends to rise during early

morning or evening due to reduced solar radiation and increased ambient moisture. The significant quadratic influence of drying time (B^2 , $p < 0.0001$) also reflects findings from (Bala and Mondol, 2020), which modeled solar drying processes and emphasized the role of climatic variability in driving nonlinear humidity behavior. Furthermore, Figure 6, 7 and 8 demonstrated seemingly strong relationship between the studied variables and air humidity. For instance, an increased number of vents from 2 to 6 resulted in higher internal humidity levels across all covering materials. The rise in internal humidity with increased vent numbers, across all covering

materials, can be attributed to greater ambient air exchange, a phenomenon supported by Al and Modrykamien (2014), showed that high ventilation rates can facilitate moisture ingress, especially under humid outdoor conditions. Among all coverings, the net material resulted in the highest humidity levels (~25%), likely due to its porous structure, which limits thermal insulation and allows more free moisture exchange with the surroundings. These results are in line with Borkakoti et al., (2025), found that net-covered dryers had significantly higher internal humidity than those enclosed with plastic sheets, thereby slowing the drying process.

Table 2. ANOVA of the effect of the studied variables on air humidity

Source	SS	Df	MS	F Value	Prob > F	
Model	467.70	5	93.54	32.86	< 0.0001*	Significant
A-No of vent	11.88	1	11.88	4.17	0.0522	
B-Time (h)	0.38	1	0.38	0.13	0.7174	
D-Type of covering material	27.01	1	27.01	9.49	0.0051	
AD	63.12	1	63.12	22.17	< 0.0001*	
B ²	271.16	1	271.16	95.25	< 0.0001*	
Residual	68.33	24	2.85			
Lack of Fit	68.17	22	3.10	40.35	0.0245*	Significant
Pure Error	0.15	2	0.077			
Cor Total	536.02	29				

Figure 6. Covering material and drying time on humidity

Figure 7. Effect of time of drying on the humidity and number of vent

Figure 8. Number of vent and fishes time on humidity

3.4. Species-specific drying responses

The graphical analysis illustrates that internal humidity levels rose with an increase in the number of vents for both Blue Whiting and Hake. Specifically, Blue Whiting showed an increase from 19% to 24%, and Hake from 18% to 23%, as vent numbers rose from 2 to 6. The slightly higher internal humidity levels recorded for Blue Whiting compared to Hake, especially under high vent configurations, may be linked to differences in initial moisture content and morphological structure. Studies by Ajala *et al.* (2023) suggest that fillet thickness, water-holding capacity, and skin permeability significantly influence species-specific drying behavior. The observed interaction between fish type and internal humidity supports this, indicating that product characteristics must be considered when designing and optimizing solar drying systems. Overall, the experimental findings of this study are consistent with recent literature emphasizing the importance of integrated system design, specifically, the interplay between dryer materials, vent configurations, and product type, in achieving optimal drying efficiency and product quality. To maximize solar dryer performance, system parameters must be tailored to local climatic conditions and the physicochemical properties of the material being dried.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that scalable, low-cost solar tent dryers can address critical

challenges in artisanal fish processing for energy-limited regions. By evaluating diverse dryer designs, the research reveals that optimizing cover materials and airflow systems leads to measurable improvements in drying efficiency, food safety, and product quality (e.g., texture, aroma, and appearance). These insights empower small-scale processors to minimize postharvest losses, boost livelihoods, and contribute to regional food security while relying on renewable energy. Several limitations should be considered. The experiments were conducted during a stable climatic period (November–December), and results may differ under conditions like high humidity or rain. The study also focused on two fish species and specific dryer configurations; broader studies are necessary for wider applicability. Moreover, the controlled setting may not fully capture real-world variables such as inconsistent fish preparation and maintenance practices. Future work should conduct year-round trials, expand testing to other species and scales, integrate technological enhancements like IoT monitoring, and evaluate economic feasibility and user adoption through participatory research.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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